

CHARACTERISTICS OF IMMUNOLOGICAL CHANGES IN BONE MARROW UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF THYMECTOMY IN AN EXPERIMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17542234>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 29th October 2025

Accepted: 30th October 2025

Online: 31st October 2025

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

To date, research by leading international scientists has proven that the primary pathogenetic factor in the development and progression of the condition after thymectomy is damage to the blood system. The study verified the link between the impact of changes in the hematopoietic system, particularly in bone marrow cells, on the immune system.

Researchers at leading global scientific centers have demonstrated that the primary pathogenetic factor in the development and progression of the condition after thymectomy is damage to the blood system. It has been shown that changes in the hematopoietic system, particularly in bone marrow cells, affect the immune system. The main consequences after thymectomy are the development of pleural aplasia, mitotic processes in the hematopoietic organs, and the total loss of low-grade differentiated cells.

Relevance. To date, research by leading international scientists has proven that the primary pathogenetic factor in the development and progression of the condition after thymectomy is damage to the blood system. The study verified the link between the impact of changes in the hematopoietic system, particularly in bone marrow cells, on the immune system.

Researchers at leading global scientific centers have demonstrated that the primary pathogenetic factor in the development and progression of the condition after thymectomy is damage to the blood system. It has been shown that changes in the hematopoietic system, particularly in bone marrow cells, affect the immune system. The main consequences after thymectomy are the development of pleural aplasia, mitotic processes in the hematopoietic organs, and the total loss of low-grade differentiated cells.

Moreover, over the past decades, more and more data have been accumulating in the literature demonstrating the important role of thymic lymphocytes in controlling the proliferation, differentiation and migration of various hematopoietic precursors (including hematopoietic stem cells).

It is significant that, in practice, removal of the thymus in adult animals does not usually result in such significant changes occurring in the bone marrow as those that occur after surgery in neonatal animals.

Unsurprisingly, literature data on the mechanisms of the thymus's influence on the hematopoietic system are extremely rare and contradictory. Therefore, the lack of progress in studying this issue is significantly reflected in experimental methods for assessing the role of lymphocytes in regulating hematopoiesis. Literary data on the mechanisms of the thymus's influence on the hematopoietic system are extremely rare and contradictory. Given the above, it seems possible to contribute to solving this pressing problem.

The aim of the study was to examine the state of the hematopoietic system in experimental animals under the influence of thymectomy.

Materials and methods. Sixty three-month-old albino rats were examined. Rats weighed no more than 160-180 g. Thymus, bone marrow, blood, and serum from this cohort of experimental rats were used for the study.

Results. In a group of experimental animals after thymus removal, patterns and mechanisms of glandular involvement in hematopoiesis regulation were determined. In animals after thymectomy, activation of lymphoid and erythrocyte hematopoiesis, bone cell granules, and a compensatory increase in the number of erythrocytes in the spleen occurred.

Hematopoietic bone marrow injury in thymectomized mice is due to an increase in granulocytomacrophage and stromal precursors, macrophage-positive and macrophage-negative hematopoietic islets, as well as a decrease in the production of colony-stimulating and erythropoietic activities.

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